

PLASMA POLYMERS FOR ADHESION PROMOTION OF GLASS FIBRES TO EPOXY RESINS

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ABSTRACT

Uncoupled unsized glass fibre tows were coated continuously with an acrylic acid/octadiene plasma copolymer. The fibres were separated for coating. It was shown that a uniform coating was attained for all fibres in the bundle. The single filament strengths of the coated and uncoated, separated control fibres were comparable but the plasma polymer coated fibres exhibited less variability (assessed using Weibull modulus). Single fibre fragmentation was used to examine the interfacial response as a function of the fibre coating. The stress transfer efficiency of Lopattanon et al gave the best quantification. The hydrocarbon plasma polymer coated fibres were only partially debonded. It was inferred that this was the result of a higher radial compressive thermal stress (than for carbon fibres which were completely debonded), as a result of the high transverse modulus of glass fibres.

KEYWORDS

Glass Fibres, Adhesion, Stress Transfer, Plasma Polymerisation

INTRODUCTION

The performance of most polymer composites has long been recognized to be reliant on an optimum interface. Therefore, it is necessary to control the interfacial phenomena that occur in the material. Plasma polymers have been used to deposit a conformal, molecularly thin functionalised coating (1,2,3), which can be used to control the degree of interfacial adhesion because the coating can be functionalised to match that required of the matrix. In the first stage of a scale-up study fibre tows (as opposed to single filaments) have been coated in this work. The degree of adhesion has been assessed using the stress transfer efficiency methodology (3).

EXPERIMENTAL

Uncoupled and unsized E-glass fibres, (Owens Corning Fiberglass) of a fibre diameter of $15.46 \mu\text{m} \pm 1.74 \mu\text{m}$ were coated with an acrylic acid and 1,7-octadiene plasma copolymer of varying composition. The fibre tows were spread using a blown-air source and wound onto the glass spools, which were placed in the reactor prior to coating. The plasma reactor, shown in Figure 1, was designed specifically to deposit a plasma polymer continuously onto the fibres within the tow. It consisted of a glass barrel section (in which polymer deposition takes place), with a helical coil of earthing braid, wound round the outside. The plasma is generated in the barrel reactor by a 13.56 MHz radio frequency power supply and matching network supplied by Coaxial Power Systems Ltd (UK). The power used for plasma deposition was 1W. The fibres were contained on spools, within the aluminium end-pieces, which were designed to prevent parasitic deposition of plasma polymer. The overall flow rate of the monomers was set at 2 sccm (cm^3 (at STP) per minute) to give the required power density for retention of chemical functionality in the plasma polymer as a pressure of $2\text{-}3 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar. The residence time of the fibres within the reactor barrel is 15 mins.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of Plasma Reactor used for Continuously Coating

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to analyse the coating chemistry. The XPS spectra were obtained with a SCIENTA 300 spectrometer operating at 2.8 kW power. Monochromated Al- α X-rays were used, focusing the X-rays to a spot size of 6 mm x 0.5 mm.

Single Fibre-Strength Measurement

Single fibres were selected at random from the coated and separated unsized fibre tow and the strength was measured at a gauge length of 6.25 mm. The control fibres (uncoated) were also passed through the reactor, but were not coated, to give a direct comparison of the effect of the coating. The sample preparation details can be found elsewhere (1). The specimens were tested in tension at a speed of 0.52 mm min⁻¹. Fibre diameter measurements were made using a Camscan Series II scanning electron microscope. At least 50 samples were tested for each fibre coating. The data was analysed using Weibull statistics.

Interfacial quantification by Single Fibre Fragmentation

The single fibre fragmentation test was carried out on the various plasma polymer coated fibres. Single fibres were extracted from the fibre tows and the test specimens were prepared as described elsewhere (4). The matrix was a 60:40 blend of LY1556 (Vantico, UK) and a flexibilising aliphatic epoxy resin Araldite GY298 (Ciba Geigy, UK) cured with 70 phr of Nadic Methylene Anhydride (Stag Polymers and Sealants, UK) and Capcure 3-800 (Henkel-Nopco, UK) at 80°C for 4 hours, followed by post-curing at 130°C for 3 hours. The samples were allowed to cool down overnight within the oven. The resin had an elastic modulus of 1.2 GPa and a tensile yield strength of 50 MPa.

The quality of the interface was quantified using the Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF) and the Stress Transfer Efficiency (STE) methodology as well as the conventional Kelly-Tyson model. The latter only gives an apparent value because the assumption of complete debonding did not apply.

In the CSTF technique (5) the shear stress profile in each fragment is calculated from the plasticity effect model (6). Debonding can be incorporated using Coulomb's law to calculate the frictional

adhesion using the radial stress given in the variational model (7). From this the fibre-tensile stress profile for each fragment is obtained which can be averaged according to equation 1.

$$CSTF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \int_0^{L_i} \sigma_f(x) dx}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i} \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of fragments, L_i is the fragment length for $i=1,2,3\dots N$, and $\sigma_f(x)$ is the tensile stress at a distance x from the fibre end. More details on the CSTF equation can be found in Tripathi et al, [5]. A Stress Transfer Efficiency (STE) (3) can also be derived from the CSTF value by normalizing it to the equivalent value for elastic-elastic conditions with a perfectly bonded interface. Thus the ideal stress transferability of a fragment represents the average tensile stress on an elastic fibre with a perfect interface, in an elastic matrix. The stress transfer efficiency is defined as:

$$STE = \frac{CSTF}{\sigma_f} \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2, shows that the underlying concentration of Si 2p, which arises from the glass fibre substrate was <1% (which is at the limit of accurate analysis by XPS). The coating thickness inferred by the XPS measurements is therefore of the order of 10 nm (0.01 μ m) which is not detectable in the fibre diameter measurements by SEM.

Figure 2: Elemental Composition of Plasma Polymer Deposited onto Glass Fibres as a Function of Acrylic Acid Content of Monomer Feed

Coated Fibres: Uniformity within a Bundle

Since Figure 3 shows that the surface functionality of the coated fibres increases with the concentration of acrylic acid in the monomer feed. However, the concentration of COOH groups is less than reported previously (2). The presence of other functional groups (COR and C=O) in the plasma deposit are considered to arise from residual water in the plasma reactor, either as adsorbate on the walls of the reactor, or the surface of the fibres. Nishioka and Shramka (8), showed that several monolayers of water will be present on an E-glass surface, which desorb only with difficulty. With fibre tows, a high surface area exists. Thus it can be expected that water will be involved in the plasma polymer deposition which probably explains the lower concentration of retained COOH groups.

Figure 3: Functional Groups Present on Fibre Surface as a Function of the Concentration of Acrylic Acid in Monomer Feed

Single Fibre Strength Measurement

From Table 1, it is seen that the average fibre strength is not significantly improved by the presence of the plasma polymer coating (within the standard deviation). The strength of the fibres was reduced from 1.46 GPa to 1.35 GPa during fibre-separation and passage through the reactor. The low initial strength arises from the fact that they were unsized and uncoupled. The Weibull modulus, on the other hand, for the plasma polymer coated glass fibres is significantly higher, showing a reduced variability in fibre-strength in the presence of the coating. This appears to suggest that either the plasma polymer protects the fibre from additional damage during sampling for strength testing, or that the large flaws responsible for the premature failures are filled by the plasma polymer.

Table 1: Single filament strength data of plasma polymer (pp) coated E-glass fibres

Fibre Coating	Average Failure Stress (GPa)	Weibull Modulus
90% Acrylic Acid pp	1.33 ± 0.56	3.94
100% 1,7-octadiene pp	1.58 ± 0.64	3.58
Unsize (As Received Fibres)	1.46 ± 0.8	3.10
Unsize (After separation and passage through the reactor)	1.35 ± 0.7	1.65

Adhesion of Plasma Polymer Functionalised E-Glass Fibres

The results of the single fibre fragmentation test are shown Table 2, it is possible to observe that the 90 % Acrylic Acid plasma polymer coated fibre exhibits the shortest fragment length at saturation (0.41 mm), the unsize fibre exhibits a similar fragment length of 0.42 mm at saturation, with the 100 % Octadiene coated fibre giving a longer average fragment length at saturation of 0.60 mm. The 100% Octadiene plasma fibre exhibits significant debonding (at an average of 44.2 % of the fragment length at saturation), whereas the 90 % Acrylic Acid coated sample only exhibited small levels of debonding (7.0 % at saturation), the unsize fibre did not debond.

Table 2: Single fibre fragmentation of plasma polymer coated E-glass fibres

Plasma Polymer coating						
Strain	Uncoated		90% Acrylic Acid		100% 1,7-octadiene	
	Average Fragment length (mm)	Average Debond (%)	Average Fragment length (mm)	Average Debond (%)	Average Fragment length (mm)	Average Debond (%)
3	1.58 (0.96)	-	6.08 (3.61)		0.82 (1.06)	N/A
4	0.96 (0.61)	-	1.71 (0.76)		1.04 (1.62)	3.35
5	0.86 (0.29)	-	0.85 (0.74)		0.93 (0.94)	12.37
6	0.63 (0.30)	-	0.50 (0.10)		0.67 (0.30)	22.67
7	0.51 (0.14)	-	0.46 (0.07)	1.65	0.64 (0.23)	27.04
8	0.48 (0.07)	-	0.43 (0.03)	2.00	0.61 (0.19)	32.50
9	0.45 (0.05)	-	0.41 (0.02)	2.76	0.61 (0.19)	35.01
10	0.43 (0.04)	-	0.41 (0.02)	3.28	0.60 (0.19)	40.80
11	0.42 (0.03)	-	0.41 (0.02)	6.98	0.60 (0.19)	44.24

Debonding of the uncoated fibres did not occur during fragmentation, which is consistent with a good interfacial bond. The constant shear analysis also supports a strong interfacial bond. However, the value of interfacial shear strength (given in Figure 4), is about twice the shear yield strength of the matrix resin (28 MPa), so that the quantification can be considered doubtful. A good bond between unsize or uncoupled glass fibre has been reported previously (9,10) so the observation is not unduly surprising.

Figure 4: Kelly-Tyson Analysis of Fragmentation Data for plasma polymer coated E-glass fibres

An alternative estimation of stress transfer can be obtained using the CSTF methodology (Figure 5). This still supports the view that adhesion of these unsized fibres is high. However, the adhesion is now apparently only marginally better than the 90% Acrylic Acid / 10% Octadiene plasma copolymer coated fibre, which exhibited only a small degree of debonding (6.98 % at saturation, as shown in Table 2). These observations seem to be consistent with a strong interfacial bond of similar magnitude. The stress transfer efficiency, has been shown [3] to be a better analysis of the stress transfer between the matrix and a fragmented fibre when the degree of debonding is high. With completely debonded fibres, CSTF can increase with applied strain, because further filament fracture cannot occur. The stress transfer efficiency (STE) is achieved by normalizing the CSTF value to that for an ideal fragment of equal length (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Analysis of the Fragmentation Data for Plasma Polymer Coated E-Glass fibres by Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF)

Figure 6: The change in Stress Transfer Efficiency of plasma polymer coated E-glass fibres during the fragmentation test

The fragmentation process leads to a different rate of length reduction so that comparison of the STE at constant strain is imprecise. The values of STE are compared at an average fragment length in Figure 7, which shows that the best interface is described by the shortest fragment length with the largest stress transfer efficiency. In this analysis the 90% Acrylic Acid / 10% Octadiene plasma copolymer coated fibres would now appear to be slightly more efficient than the untreated glass fibres, although within the error bars the difference may not be significant.

Figure 7: Stress Transfer Efficiency of plasma polymer coated E-glass fibres as a function of fragment length

One of the most interesting observations concerns the 100% Octadiene plasma polymer coated fibres, which only partially debond during the experiment. With carbon fibres, complete interfacial debonding was observed at low applied strains. With carbon fibres the plasma polymer completely masked the underlying adhesive ability of the fibre, in this case some appear to be retained, yet the functional chemistry does not appear to be significantly different. This can be either a strong residual water effect on the fibre surface functional chemistry, or a result of differing residual stresses. The good adhesion of unsized or uncoupled E-glass fibres has been observed before. These data strongly supported the latter argument because without an obvious chemical mechanism the thermal stresses which are compressive in the radial direction provide the most plausible mechanism. It can be understood that the radial modulus of E-glass at 76 GPa is much higher than 14 GPa for carbon fibres of smaller diameter.

CONCLUSIONS

Plasma polymerisation was utilised to deposit a functionalised plasma polymer size continuously onto E-glass fibre tows. XPS showed that the fibres are uniformly coated within the tow. The variability in the strength of the fibres (as measured by Weibull modulus) has been reduced by the presence of the plasma polymer coating. The presence of the plasma polymer coating has also changed the interfacial response of the fibre. The STE methodology appears to be a good data analysis for quantification of the adhesion.

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REFERENCES

1. Kettle AP, Beck AJ, O'Toole L, Jones FR, Short RD. "Plasma polymerisation for molecular engineering of carbon-fibre surfaces for optimized composites". *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 1997, 57(8), 1023-1032
2. Lopattananon N, Kettle AP, Tripathi D, Beck AJ, Duval E, France RM, Short RD, Jones FR. "Interface molecular engineering of carbon-fibre composites". *Composites Pt A.* 1999, 30A (1), 49-57
3. Lopattananon N, Hayes SA, Jones FR. "Stress transfer function for interface assessment in composites using plasma copolymer functionalised carbon fibres". *J. Adhesion.* 2002, 78, 313-350
4. Marks, DJ and Jones, FR. "Plasma polymerized coatings for engineered interfaces for enhanced composite performance", *Composites Pt A*, 2002, 33, 1293-1302
5. Tripathi D, Jones FR. "Measurement of the load-bearing capability of the fibre/matrix interface by single-fibre fragmentation". *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 1997, 57 (8), 925-935
6. Tripathi D, Chen FP, Jones FR. "A comprehensive model to predict the stress fields in a single fibre composite". *J. Comp. Mat.* 1996, 30 (14), 1514-1538
7. Nairn JA. "A variational mechanics analysis of the stresses around breaks in embedded fibers". *Mech. Mater.* 1992, 13 (2), 131-154
8. Nishioka GM, Schramka JA. "Desorption of water from glass fibres". In: *Ishida H, Kumar G, Editors. Molecular Characterisation of Composite Interfaces.* New York: Plenum 1983. p.387

9. Cheng TH, Jones FR, Wang D. "Effect of fiber conditioning on the interfacial shear strength of glass-fiber composites". *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 1993, 48 (1-4), 89-96
10. Berg J, Jones FR. "The role of sizing resins, coupling agents and their blends on the formation of the interphase in glass fibre composites". *Composites Pt A.* 1998, 29A(9-10), 1261-1272